

offspring:parent regression was the least variable of the estimates among populations (indicated by the low CV). Among the characters, mesocotyl length estimates were least variable.

This means early generation selection for seedling emergence should be more effective using mesocotyl length. Early generation selection using coleoptile and seedling length can be done only in selected crosses. Otherwise, selection would be more effective in later generations, accompanied by progeny testing. ■

Narrow sense heritability (Hn) estimates for mesocotyl, coleoptile, and seedling length in rice, measured by variance partitioning (VPSP) and offspring:parent F₃:F₂ regression (regr) and correlation (corr).

Cross	Hn estimates											
	Mesocotyl				Coleoptile				Seedling			
	VPSP	Regr	Corr	Mean	VPSP	Regr	Corr	Mean	VPSP	Regr	Corr	Mean
ITA212/Nato	53.7	64.7	49.0	55.8	30.4	40.7	54.2	41.8	48.3	26.7	35.0	36.7
TN1/Nato	30.6	71.4	63.3	55.1	67.6	35.6	48.7	50.6	30.3	27.4	33.2	30.3
TN1/ITA323	61.8	71.4	84.1	72.4	61.6	37.8	46.1	48.5	50.3	33.2	20.0	34.5
IR64/ITA212	50.0	52.7	63.1	61.1	21.2	18.7	26.2	22.0	35.2	26.5	40.3	34.0
Mean	49.0	65.1	64.9	59.7	45.2	33.2	43.8	40.7	41.0	28.5	32.1	33.9
CV	26.9	13.5	22.3	11.9	50.5	29.8	27.9	38.1	23.9	11.2	26.9	26.3

Genetic and cytoplasmic sources of IR varieties 1967-84

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Genetic diversity of cytoplasm sources for released varieties is important because genetic uniformity could lead to devastating disease epidemics. We used a computer program written in PASCAL to examine the pedigrees of 27 *Oryza sativa* L. IR lines released 1967-84.

The pedigrees show that the 27 varieties can be traced back to 26 ancestors,

of which 5 appear only once. Ten ancestors comprise 75% of the relative genetic contribution. Three dominate in mean relative genetic contribution: Dee-geo-woo-gen, 16%; Cina, 12.6%; and Latisail, 12.6%. Dee-geo-woo-gen appears in the pedigree of 26 of the 27 varieties; Cina and Latisail are in the pedigrees of all varieties. This makes the 27 varieties examined more or less related. More ancestors have been integrated into recent varieties.

Four cultivars were ultimate maternal ancestors, and thus contributed cytoplasm to all 27 varieties (see table). Cina contributed its cytoplasm to 22 of the 27 varieties, and is the most

Cytoplasm parents for 27 varieties released at IRRI.

Cytoplasm parent	IR lines				
Nam Sagui 19 Cina	IR52	IR54			
	IR5	IR28	IR38	IR50	
	IR8	IR29	IR40	IR56	
	IR20	IR30	IR42	IR58	
	IR22	IR32	IR45	IR60	
	IR24	IR34	IR46		
Marong-Paroc Arikarai	IR26	IR36	IR48		
	IR43	IR44			
	IR62				

important contributor of both nuclear and cytoplasmic genes to the IR varieties. ■

Effect of germinating condition and plant growth regulator on rate of twin seedlings from polyembryonic rice

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Polyembryonic rice—characterized by twin seedlings—is a good genetical tool for apomixis research. We studied four selected heritable polyembryonic rices.

Adventitious embryos had low frequencies (2.6-5.1%). The apparent primary mode of polyembryonic rice is twin seedlings, but there is an internal relationship between the rate of twin seedlings and the rate of adventitious embryos.

We experimented with the effect of germinating condition on twin seedling rate in Shuang 3 (indica), Shuang 13

Table 1. Rates of twin seedlings under different germinating conditions.

Variety	Rate (%) of twin seedlings							
	Germinated in distilled water (25°C)	Germinated in N6 (25°C) (with no pretreatment)	Germinated in N6 media (25 °C) with wet pretreatment ^a (5 h)					
			0°C	10°C	20°C	30°C	40°C	50°C
Shuang 3 (indica)	41.0	48.4	17.1	65.8	67.5	75.0	70.5	42.5
Shuang 13 (indica)	5.3	7.7	5.3	12.9	7.4	13.2	6.9	16.6
Lu 52 (japonica)	6.5	13.2	6.7	11.1	7.9	13.1	8.8	24.5
Alixisini (japonica)	2.0	3.1	0	1.9	3.9	1.9	1.6	4.4

^a There was no germination at 60°C.

(indica), Lu 52 (japonica), and Alixisini (japonica). Germinating seeds without hulls resulted in higher rates of twin seedlings than germinating seeds with hulls. The highest increase was 3.8%.

The rate of twin seedlings increased when the germination test was done in

N6 media. The twin seedling rate varied with pregermination treatment at different temperatures (Table 1). The optimum pretreatment temperature was 50°C for two japonicas and one indica and 30°C for the other indica. At optimum temperature, the rate of twin seedlings